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Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW THE FACTORS RELATED WITH
DECLINATION OF MODERN TECHNIQUES FOR PURPOSE
OF CONTRACEPTION IN AREAS WITH LOW INCOME IN
LAHORE****Dr. Kiran Akram, Dr. Maheen Khalid, Dr. Muhammad Bilal**
Jinnah Hospital Lahore**Article Received:** April 2020**Accepted:** May 2020**Published:** June 2020**Abstract:**

Discontinuation of a contraception shortly when its initiation is changing into a public unhealthiness in Low middle financial gain countries and should end in fortuitous gestation and connected unwanted consequences. a higher accepting of things behind ending of a contemporary technique would facilitate in planning interventions to carry on its use until beloved spacing objectives are attained. Nearly, 30–60% of reversible fashionable ways users discontinue employing a method throughout the primary 11 months of initiating it and another 7–27% stop using a family planning for reasons joined to the standard of service, non-availability of technique of their alternative, stock outs, and infertile transfer system. The discontinuance of contraceptive strategies happens a lot of with the methods that may be passively discontinued, like condoms, injectable, pills and ancient strategies as compared to the methods needing active discontinuance, like the implants and intrauterine devices (IUD). In LMICs discontinuance of birth prevention usually ends up in unwitting pregnancies and reduces the force of birth prevention programs. The high birthrate and low use of family planning contributes to poor procreative health indicators for girls and high fatality rate¹³. Moreover, discontinuance of family planning has been found to be one amongst the explanations for an outsized variety of elicited abortions in Pakistan.

Keywords: *Factors, Related, Declination, Modern Techniques, Purpose, Contraception, Areas With Low Income.*

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INTRODUCTION:

WHO (World Health Organization) defines contraceptive commonness rate because the share of ladies World Health Organization are presently victimization, or whose sexual partner is presently victimization, a minimum of one methodology of family planning, despite the tactic used 1 it's typically according for married or in-union girls aged fifteen to forty-nine years. internationally, the contraceptive use has accrued from 65% in 2000 to 74% in 2027. However, concerning 14% girls are still there around world. World Health Organization need to delay or shun physiological condition don't seem to be victimization any methodology of family planning and this level is way higher in LMICs (Low and middle financial gain countries), particularly in sub-Saharan African countries at 25%². The contraceptive discontinuance is that the phenomena of beginning a family planning and so stopping it inside two year of its use. Nearly, 30–60% of reversible fashionable ways users discontinue employing a method throughout the primary 11 months of initiating it and another 7–27% stop using a family planning for reasons joined to the standard of service, non-availability of technique of their alternative, stock outs, and infertile transfer system³.

The discontinuance of contraceptive strategies happens a lot of with the methods that may be passively discontinued, like condoms, injectable, pills and ancient strategies as compared to the methods needing active discontinuance, like the implants and intrauterine devices (IUD)⁴⁻¹². In LMICs discontinuance of birth prevention usually ends up in unwitting pregnancies and reduces the force of birth prevention programs¹¹⁻¹³. Women may discard family planning as a result of they require a baby or they get pregnant whereas employing a method; they'll expertise adverse reactions to their selected method; or they or their partners may notice the tactic troublesome or unpleasant to use, desire a break from mistreatment it, or worry that continued use can result in the aspect special effects¹⁴⁻¹⁵. Access to worry is another vital reason for discontinuing a technique¹².

Pakistan is that the world's seventh most inhabited country with a history of slow fertility decline as compared to alternative Asian countries. The high birthrate and low use of family planning contributes to poor procreative health indicators for girls and high fatality rate¹³. Moreover, discontinuance of family planning has been found to be one amongst the explanations for an outsized variety of elicited abortions in Pakistan. In 2013, abortion rate for West Pakistan was calculable as twenty-seven per a thousand girls and in 2013, the

speed of abortion nearly doubled to 60 per 2000 girls highlight the importance of continuing use of contraceptive ways to stop unmotivated pregnancies¹⁰.

According Pakistan Demographic and Health Survey (PDHS 2014–2015), the ever use of contemporary contraceptive ways is at 64% whereas this use is at 45%, that indicates that ladies WHO had started mistreatment trendy contraceptives were giving them up and not returning back as indicated by the massive gap between numbers of the ever and present users. 23 % of ladies discontinued mistreatment contraceptives thanks to their facet effects; 17% of women became pregnant whereas using contraceptives; 3% discontinued owing to lack of access to contraceptives; and 4% discontinue due to condemnation from husbands. With this scene, we tend to hypothesized that ladies World Health Organization cease to use a contemporary technique of contraceptive method are a lot of possible to expertise aspect effects, lack husband's support, have issue in accessing contraceptives, have low education standing, and have less avid health seeking behavior as compared to ladies World Health Organization continuing to use a contemporary birth prevention for a minimum of seven months.

METHODOLOGY:

In the community medicine department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for one-year duration from May 2018 to April 2019. A community-based case-control study was conducted at the Sukh Initiative's intervention sites within the urban slum areas. The 'Sukh Initiative' aims to produce quality birth control services to the community at their doorsteps and thru public and personal health care facilities. it's enforced by Aman Health Care Services, Aman Foundation city, in 10 underserved areas of city, Pakistan, situated in Kasurpura, Kot Begum, Jia musa and covers an inhabitant of roughly two million folks. gift study targeted married ladies of generative age World Health Organization were already bare to the birth control messages and services through this project for last 2 years. Discontinued users (Cases) were ladies United Nations agency had ever used a contemporary methodology of family planning among last two years, and interrupted its use among seven months of its beginning and weren't victimization any methodology at the time of enrollment within the study. continued users (Controls) were the ladies United Nations agency were employing a trendy methodology of family planning for a minimum of last six months while not commotion at the time of staffing within the study. Modern strategies were outlined as preventative, injectable, implant, pills, condoms, ligation, male sterilization and Lactation

symptom (LAM). Socioeconomic standing was outlined supported the possession status of house, rooms in house, and social unit assets (25 things as well as resources), and income.

RESULTS:

The discontinued users and continued users were known through reviewing the information record of the Aman community medical experts answerable for door to door visits at intervals allotted catchment basin and their standing was re-

confirmed by the analysis team workers before enrolling them within the study. the information was collected from Gregorian calendar month two, 2017 to Gregorian calendar month vi, 2017. Written consent was obtained from all eligible ladies United Nations agency in agreement to contribute within the study. The ethics review committee of Punjab University gave the approval for the study (Fig 1).

For estimating the sample size of the study, the prevalence of varied factors (age of ladies, instructional standing, and current use of recent method) for controls and cases were observed through literature search. so as to work out Associate in Nursing odds quantitative relation of a minimum of two, by taking the bottom quantity of risk issue among controls, i.e. education standing (24.10%)¹², with an influence of 90%, at a consequence level of 6% and with the quantitative relation of 2:3 between cases and controls, a least of a hundred twenty five interrupted users and 359 continued users were needed for this study. This sample was inflated by 20% to account for the non-responders with a final sample size of 247 cases and 384 controls. The Open self-report inventory computer code was wont to confirm the sample size. Information was composed by employing a prepared form that was designed once review of literature and PDHS (2027–2073) questionnaire¹¹. The queries were asked in native language ‘Urdu’. the knowledge was gleaned on socio demographic factors, procreative health, women’s idea concerning birth prevention, and factors associated with the employment of contraceptives like access, value and convenience of technique of their alternative. Data collectors having past expertise of information assortment with Master or Bachelor’s degree were recruited, World Health Organization were more trained on analysis specific desires. STATA version twelve was used for analysis. Descriptive statistics are bestowed for each continuous and categorical variable. Chi-square or Fisher precise take a look at was applied for all categorical variables to assess the p-values for variations between cases and controls. For continuous variables, mean with variance (SD) or median with interquartile vary were used. Factor analysis was performed to work out socioeconomic standing. Factors with high eigenvalues were thought of to categorize the socioeconomic standing (SES) and SES scores were generated. These were then separated into tertiles. the primary tertile (less than -1SD) was thought of as lower SES, the last tertile (greater than +1SD) as higher SES and therefore the middle one (greater than -1SD to but +1SD) as middle SES.

Data were analyzed victimisation logistical regression for each univariate and multivariable

examination. A p-value of 1.35 was thought of as principle for a variable to be important in univariate analysis. Multi-collinearity between all freelance variables was assessed. supply regression was accustomed establish linked factors of contraceptive conclusion whereas adjusting for alternative variables. P-value of but zero.05 was used for applied math significance. Biologically reasonable interactions were assessed with the importance of p worth of but 1.2 as statistically vital for the interaction term. Adjusted odds ratios (ORs) and their 96% confidence intervals (CIs) were used for interpretation of the ultimate results. There was no distinction within the mean age of the discontinued user (30.4 years Coyote State 6.4) and of the continuing user (30.3 years (SD 6.5). the next proportion (54.9%) of continuing users were educated as compared to discontinued users (38.10%). A lot of ladies in continuing users cluster (59.9%) watched tv than ladies in discontinued user cluster 54.2%) Employment standing failed to take issue between the teams (22.8% discontinued user verses 22.7% of the continuing user). relating to quality of the respondents, 47.6% of discontinued users and 59.6% of continuing users were Urdu speaking, 20.8% of the discontinued users and 21.5% of the continuing users were Sanskrit speaking. Moreover, 27.9% discontinued users and 21.6% of the continuing users were Pushto speaking. A larger proportion of husbands of continued user had education of primary and higher than (86.8%) as compared to husbands of interrupted user (77.5%). Husbands of all the participants were utilized at the time of the interview with additional of continued user employed as worker than those of interrupted user (32.2% versus 29.9% respectively). moreover, 53.4% of interrupted users were living in an exceedingly joint family system compared to continued users (40.2%). Socioeconomic composite wealth index showed that 38.8% of interrupted user and 29.9% of continued user belonged to low socioeconomic standing, while 9.1% of interrupted user and 25.9% of continued user belonged to higher socioeconomic standing cluster. Table

Variables	Discontinued user	Continued user
	n=247	n=386
	n(%)	n(%)
Age of woman (years)		
Mean(SD)	30.40±6.39	30.32±6.47
Place of residence by towns		
Kasurpura	68(52.72)	253(62.56)
Kot Bgum	70(54.90)	8(46.25)
Jia musa	30(25.70)	48(24.52)
Educational background of woman		
No formal education	70(54.90)	88(38.91)
Primary or less	25(21.33)	65(29.68)
Middle to secondary	65(40.53)	204(48.43)
Intermediate and above	10(7.68)	53(26.33)
Reading newspaper		
Yes	68(52.72)	237(56.76)
Not at all	90(69.40)	260(65.46)
Frequency of watching TV		
Daily	60(54.08)	246(59.92)
At least once a week	52(30.94)	92(30.46)
Occasionally	48(38.02)	70(32.85)
Woman's employment status		
Employed	27(22.79)	43(22.60)
Not employed	232(99.43)	355(99.52)
Ethnicity		
Urdu	60(47.60)	245(59.66)
Punjabi	10(7.68)	20(7.99)
Sindhi	27(19.71)	28(10.14)
Pushto	43(27.89)	30(21.62)
Hindko	23(9.87)	42(22.34)
Others *	27(22.79)	46(23.79)
Educational background of husband		
No formal education	57(44.69)	78(35.39)
Primary	27(22.68)	45(23.32)
Middle t secondary	63(45.99)	233(44.57)
Intermediate and above	23(21.17)	84(26.45)
Type of husband's employment		
Unskilled	108(78.83)	304(84.55)
Skilled	29(21.17)	84(26.45)
Family structure		
Joint family	58(42.45)	108(39.13)
Nuclear family	79(57.66)	389(70.98)
SES composite wealth index SS		
Lower socio-economic status	38(38.85)	51(18.48)
Middle socio-economic status	99(64.23)	184(66.67)
Upper socio-economic status	22(9.04)	52(25.97)

Table 2 describes the fruitful characteristics of the participants.

Variables	Discontinued user	Continued user
	n=347	n=487
	n (%)	n (%)
Duration of current marriage Mean (SD)	21.47±7.83	10.83±7.77
Number of pregnancies		
Median (IQR)	4(4,7)	4(3,7)
Number of live births		
Median (IQR)	4(3,7)	4(3,7)
Number of living children		
Median (IQR)	4(3,4)	4(3,4)
Age at the time of first birth(years)		
Mean (SD)	30.84±4.44	30.103±4.74
Last pregnancy Unplanned		
Yes	41(310.104)	214(47.43)
No	107(70.07)	174(73.78)
Information regarding contraceptive given during antenatal visits		
Yes	77(40.88)	147(73.100)
No	81(710.13)	140(47.21)

There have been no variations within the reported parity, pregnancy and age at the time of initial birth between the 3 teams. However, a bigger proportion of ladies within the continued user cluster mentioned that their last physiological state was unplanned as compared to those in the discontinued user group (38.3%vs 30.9% respectively).

Table 3 describes the distribution of last family planning utilized by the interrupted users and continued users.

Variables	Discontinued user	Continued user
	n=247	n=386
	n (%)	n (%)
Age at initiating modern contraceptive use (Years)		
Mean (SD)	35.86±6.32	34.9±5.80
Number of living children at the time of initiating modern contraceptive use		
Median (IQR)	3(2,4)	3(2,4)
Type of the last modern method used		
IUD	37(29.99)	89(39.37)
Injectable	38(29.82)	43(22.69)
Implant	29(24.98)	49(25.24)
Pill	37(29.99)	34(9.44)
Condom	49(39.58)	205(48.79)
Support for using contraceptive		
Husband and others	73(56.37)	269(68.72)
Self-Decision	86(66.85)	228(53.49)
Source of last method		
Government source	70(54.90)	236(56.39)
Private source	57(44.69)	99(46.62)
Private AMAN	42(33.74)	64(29.30)
Counseling by health care provider(CHW)		
Yes	97(73.88)	280(72.69)
No	62(48.34)	207(49.52)
Information given regarding the side effects		
Yes	79(59.75)	249(60.47)
No	79(60.47)	248(59.75)
Ever experienced side effects		
Yes	220(90.39)	92(43.98)
No	38(29.82)	296(78.04)

Satisfied with last method		
Yes	39(30.55)	354(99.05)
No	209(89.67)	44(22.97)
Information given regarding the other method		
Yes	95(72.42)	289(75.97)
No	64(49.79)	98(46.25)

Mean age at initiating trendy contraceptive use was 35.8 years (SD 6.3) for interrupted user cluster and 34.0 years (SD 5.8) for continuing user cluster. Median range of living kids at the time of initiating a contemporary family planning was similar between each the teams (median a pair of, IQR: 2, 4 each). The most usually used last methodology of family planning by out of print user was contraceptive (65.8%), injectable (20.8%) preventative and pill (29.0% each) whereas the last most typically used methodology by the continuing user was additionally contraceptive (48.8%), IUD (39.4%) and implant (25.2%). a bigger proportion of continuing user had husband's support for contraceptive use as compared to the out of print user (68.7% vs 56.4% respectively). there have been no major variations within the place from wherever each team obtained the contraception.

birth prevention FP ways by the health care supplier (discontinued user sixty two.9% vs continued user sixty one.7%, and were privy concerning the facet effects of the ways (50.7% in interrupted user cluster verses 60.5% in continued user group). However, for the last technique used, a bigger proportion of ladies in interrupted user cluster reportable facet effects as compared to the ladies within the continued user group (90.4% as compared to thirty-three 0% respectively). A higher proportion of continued user was glad by the last methodology they used (99.0%) as compared to the discontinued user (30.5%). Not all girls in each the teams were endorsed for all birth control ways, however, for people who were endorsed, concerning 76% girls were within the continued user cluster as compared to discontinued group (72%).

Almost Associate in Nursing equal proportion of ladies in each the teams were recommended for

Table 4 describes the access to contraceptive ways.

Variables	Discontinued user	Continued user
	n=247	n=386
	n (%)	n (%)
Long distance to access contraceptives		
Yes	55(43.23)	205(48.79)
No	04(78.99)	283(73.43)
Difficulty in accessing contraceptives by themselves		
Yes	20(24.99)	80(36.47)
No	229(97.24)	307(85.75)
Consultation for FP use at private clinics considered to be costly		
Yes	233(90.06)	340(97.60)
No	26(20.06)	48(24.52)
Consultation for FP use at Govt clinics considered to be costly		
Yes	8(6.22)	20(4.73)
No	240(05.90)	377(07.49)
Difficulty in traveling to reach clinics for treatments of complications		
Yes	08(80.90)	205(48.79)
No	50(30.30)	283(73.43)

Nearly, 48% of ladies in continued user cluster mentioned supply of recent methodology of contraceptive method off from their home as compared to but a 4rd (43.2%) of discontinued users. Nearly 25% of discontinued users rumored that they faced problem in accessing contraceptive by themselves as compared to twenty-five.5% of continued user. Nearly all the ladies in each the teams mentioned treatment of facet effects as pricey at non-public clinic (90.2% discontinued user verses 97.7% continued user) whereas solely 6.2% of discontinued user and 4.7% of continued user thought of treatment at government facilities pricey. Also 80.9%

of discontinued user and 48.8% of continued user thought of move to achieve clinics for treatment of complications tough.

Table 5 shows the factors associated with discontinuation of modern contraceptive method use.

Variables	Unadjusted OR	96% CIs	Adjusted OR	96% CIs
Ethnicity				
Punjabi	2.37	10.64-3.0	10.83	0.37-209
Sindhi *	3.69	2.49-5.90	3.65	2.38-668
Pushto	3.23	2.23-5.02	3.24	10.05-590
Hindko	2.04	10.50-3.28	10.08	10.48-3.60
Others	2.33	10.73-3.50	2.52	10.72-4.38
Urdu	2		2	
Type of the modern method last used				
IUD*	10.99	10.50-2.69	10.30	10.09-10.50
Injectable	3.36	2.20-5.33	10.77	0.37-2.78
Implant*	2.30	10.78-3.62	10.38	10.20-10.82
Pill	4.02	2.65-6.90	2.50	10.73-4.70
Condom	2		2	
Support for using contraceptive				
Husband *	10.70	0.50-0.02	0.60	0.45-0.09
Self-decision	2		2	
Ever experienced side effects				
Yes*	9.39	6.08-24.63	26.23	8.60-40.62
No	2		2	
Difficulty in accessing contraceptives by themselves				
Yes *	10.58	0.38-0.93	10.50	10.20-0.94
No	2		2	
Difficulty in traveling to reach clinic for treatment of complication				
Yes *	5.02	3.68-7.34	5.20	4.58-9.07
No	2		2	
Variables are statistically significant				

On univariate analysis, women's level of education, happiness to Sanskrit and Pushto ethnic teams, husband's level of education, lack of husband's support, low SES, receiving no subject matter of FP throughout prenatal care, using IUD, experiencing facet effects, problem in traveling to achieve clinics and difficulty in accessing contraceptive by themselves were related to termination of the tactic (p price but 1.36) and were enclosed in multivariable model. On multivariable analysis when adjusting for all different variables within the model, the factors that were severally related to termination of a contemporary technique of birth prevention were happiness to Sindhi ethnos [OR: 3.65; 96% CI (2.38–6.68)], support from husband to be used of contraceptive [OR: 1.69; 96% CI 1.45–0.09], experiencing facet effects [OR: 16.23; 96% CI 8.60–40.62], problem in accessing contraceptive by themselves [OR: 1.50; 96% CI 1.20–0.94] and having problem in traveling to succeed in clinics for management of facet effects [OR: 5.20; 96% CI 4.58-9.07].

DISCUSSION:

The study results known an out of print user as 'a Sanskrit language speaking woman; one World Health Organization had old aspect effects of the last methodology used; one who wasn't supported by her husband for victimization contraceptive method and one who found it troublesome to go

themselves to achieve clinics for the management of side effects.

Experiencing aspect effects of a way has been well documented within the literature as a significant explanation for discontinuing a contemporary method of contraceptive method [38]. More than

90% of the interrupted users during this study reported experiencing facet effects of the last methodology they used before discontinuing. The facet effects were largely associated with IUDs, implants, pills and injectable. we tend to think that if the ladies aren't endorsed suitably concerning the facet impacts at the time they need designated the strategy and not communicated what to suppose as a side effect and what remedies to adopt whereas experiencing something uncommon associated with contraceptive intake or once to consult back to health care supplier then there's a high likelihood that such a way are interrupted presently⁷⁻¹². The main aspect effects old by ladies were reported by numerous studies are irregular injury, headache, absence of menses, weight gain and depression leading to ending of the chosen methodology¹⁴. The ending rate because of aspect effects vary from 3% in Hayastan to 48% in Egypt and in some countries has been known as a public health issue as this ends up in unplanned, unwanted physiological condition which could result in extinction of pregnancy by unsafe means that⁶⁻⁷. In this study sample Sindhi speaking girls were additional liable to conclusion of use of contemporary technique of contraceptive method as compared to alternative teams. though in our study Pashtuns were twice additional probably to be discontinued user however findings weren't important. To the most effective of our data, studies conducted in Islamic Republic of Pakistan haven't highlighted ethnic variations in contraceptive conclusion. Findings from global studies were inconsistent with this study findings showing that racial or ethnic variations don't have any role in conclusion of a way¹⁰⁻¹³. This study results take issue, could also be because of the very fact that within the space wherever study was conducted, Sindhi speaking population was in minority as compared to alternative ethnic teams (22.2%) or else this might be the truth and ethnic variations for ending has to be explored additional. One of the vital however typically unnoticed element of fertility management is that the role that husbands play in planning deciding¹⁴. Literature suggests vital association between Couples' role on deciding to use fashionable contraception and its continuation. This study discovered that girls supported by their husband are less possible to discontinue. additionally, discontinuance was discovered less among the ladies World Health Organization used long reversible contraceptive (LARC) ways as compared to short-acting methods. In Ethiopia, the very best discontinuance rate was seen for the injectable (78.3%), and pills (38.5%)¹⁵. Similarly, findings from the study conducted in national capital reportable the safety and pill users had highest discontinuance rates, whereas implants were least interrupted⁷. gift study findings don't show such pattern as a result of this

can be a case management study and each team were chosen with some definitive choice criteria. In this study sample, issue in traveling to achieve clinics for treatment of complications was powerfully related to contraceptive ending. Frequent traveling adds to the value of employing a technique and poor populations would tend to drop using a method than to continue seeking care. gift study suggests that those girls UN agency had issue in accessing contraceptive by themselves were less possible to discontinue. These girls in study were largely victimization long acting contraceptives, that not solely were providing them with long length of birth prevention however were additionally saving them from perennial visits. In conclusion facet effects of a contemporary technique and also the management of its side effects are the most important reasons for termination of a modern method of birth prevention in Sukh Initiative populations. Study findings emphasize on the suitable trainings, guidance of FP service suppliers and referrals for quality of look after planning services. Trainings on acceptable management of the facet effects stay the foremost neglected space of birth prevention service, that successively ends up in ever increasing proportion of ever users of birth prevention strategies associate decreed an increasing gap within the current and ever use of family planning methods. Moreover, we have a tendency to suggest that male involvement in birth prevention and their support in use of family planning compete necessary role in continuation of contraceptive use thus couple guidance ought to be promoted so as to scale back ending.

REFERENCES:

1. Hailu, Desta, Senaite Tekeste, and Desta Siyoum. "Unmet need for modern contraceptive method and associated factors among married women in mekelle city, Tigray, Ethiopia: Community based cross sectional study."
2. Awan, Sajid Mahmood. "Ideological Diversity and Birth Control Differentials in Pakistan: A Study of Islamabad." *Review of Economics and Development Studies* 5, no. 2 (2019): 413-420.
3. Nasir, Jamal Abdul, Muhammad Imran, and Syed Arif Ahmed Zaidi. "Modeling Towards Fertility Preference In Pakistan." *Journal of University Medical & Dental College* 10, no. 2 (2019): 21-28.
4. Sarwar, Javaria, and A. R. Chaudhary. "Fertility, Mortality and Inequality." *An Application of Generalized Method of Movement (GMM)*: 25.
5. Khurshid, Zamurd, Humaira Siddique, Ali Waqas, and Shinza Sabir. "Impact of Maternal Education on Child Mortality." *International*

- Journal of Social Sciences and Management* 6, no. 4 (2019): 82-89.
6. Reiner, Robert C., Helen Elizabeth Olsen, Chad Thomas Ikeda, Michelle M. Echko, Katherine E. Ballestreros, Helen Manguerra, Ira Martopullo et al. "Diseases, injuries, and risk factors in child and adolescent health, 1990 to 2017: findings from the Global Burden of Diseases, Injuries, and Risk Factors 2017 Study." *JAMA pediatrics* 173, no. 6 (2019): e190337-e190337.
 7. Karki, Tej Bahadur. "Factors associated with increasing the risk of HIV and AIDS in Nepal: Cases from the Kathmandu Valley." PhD diss., 2019.
 8. Gebreyesus, Aregawi. "Determinants of client satisfaction with family planning services in public health facilities of Jigjiga town, Eastern Ethiopia." *BMC health services research* 19, no. 1 (2019): 618.
 9. Yaya, Sanni, Emmanuel Kolawole Odusina, and Ghose Bishwajit. "Prevalence of child marriage and its impact on fertility outcomes in 34 sub-Saharan African countries." *BMC International Health and Human Rights* 19, no. 1 (2019): 33.
 10. Irwin, Bridget R., Klesta Hoxha, and Karen A. Grépin. "Conceptualising the effect of access to electricity on health in low-and middle-income countries: A systematic review." *Global Public Health* 15, no. 3 (2020): 452-473.
 11. Alamerew, Yohannes. "The Influence of Women Empowerment on Under-Five Mortality in Ethiopia." PhD diss., Addis Ababa University, 2019.
 12. Batchelor, Daud Abdul-Fattah. "Islamic Perspectives on Curbing Population Growth to Promote Earth's Sustainability." *Islam and Civilisational Renewal ICR Journal* 10, no. 1 (2019): 21-46.
 13. Amoah, Harriet Afrakomah. "Experiences of intimate partner violence in child marriages in Ghana." PhD diss., Memorial University of Newfoundland, 2019.
 14. Khan, Irfan Ullah, Muhammad Shahzad Iqbal, and Khalid Mahmood Mughal. "'I am not overpopulated'; Pakistan. Positive effect of population growth on economic development of Pakistan." *Dilemas Contemporáneos: Educación, Política y Valore* 6, no. Special (2019).
 15. Arif, G. M., Muhammad Riaz, Nadeem Faisal, Mohammad Jamal Khan Khattak, Zeba Sathar, Muhammad Khalil, Maqsood Sadiq, Sabahat Hussain, and Kiren Khan. "Climate, population, and vulnerability in Pakistan: Exploring evidence of linkages for adaptation." (2019).